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● Nomenclatural notes on *Achillides* (Lepidoptera; Papilionidae)

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Abstract: Nomenclatural problems in *Papilio* subgenus *Achillides*, grouped into categories of similar cases, are clarified. Two new replacement names, *Papilio krishna schaeffleri* **nom. nov.** and *Papilio ulysses zizi* **nom. nov.**, and five new synonyms are proposed.

Keywords: homonym, ICZN Code, *Papilio*, replacement name, synonym

● 关于翠凤蝶亚属 *Achillides* 的命名法注释（鳞翅目；凤蝶科）

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摘要: 本文对凤蝶属 *Papilio* 翠凤蝶亚属 *Achillides* 中的命名法问题进行了澄清, 并将相似案例归类。文中提出了两个新的替代名——*Papilio krishna schaeffleri* **nom. nov.**和 *Papilio ulysses zizi* **nom. nov.**, 以及五个新异名。

关键词: 同名, 国际动物命名法规, 凤蝶属, 替代名, 异名

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● Introduction

The ‘gloss papilios’, *Achillides* Hübner, [1819], are currently regarded as a subgenus of *Papilio* Linnaeus, 1758 (Condamine *et al.* 2023) containing about 30 species and ranging from South Asia to the Far East and Australasia. A number of nomenclatural issues in the subgenus have been found, which are enumerated here with proposed solutions.

● Nomenclatural Notes

1. Junior Secondary Homonyms

Secondary homonymy occurs when a taxon is moved to a genus containing another taxon with the same species-group name (see ICZN Code Article 57.3.1). When secondary homonymy applies the junior name is invalid, and the next oldest available name for the taxon replaces it. However, if these taxa are subsequently placed in separate genera secondary homonymy no longer applies and the junior name is reinstated as the valid taxon name (see Articles 59.2–59.4), unlike a junior primary homonym which is permanently invalid. *Achillides* is generally not accepted as a valid genus (Munroe [1961]; Hancock 1983; Racheli & Bozano 2024) and DNA analysis suggests it is at best treated as a subgenus of *Papilio* Linnaeus, 1758 (Zakharov *et al.* 2004; Condamine *et al.* 2013, 2023). Four cases of secondary homonymy resulting from new taxa described between 2004 and 2006 by authors who, following the opinion of Page & Treadaway (2003), treated *Achillides* as a genus are discussed here:

1.1 *Achillides ulysses scylla* Dufek, Schäffler & Schmidbauer, 2005: 1, fig.

This name is normally regarded as a subspecies of *Papilio ulysses* Linnaeus, 1758.

A junior secondary homonym of *Papilio scylla* Linnaeus, 1763 (currently *Catopsilia scylla* [Linnaeus, *in* Johansson, 1763] – Pieridae: Coliadinae) (Honey & Scoble 2001: 378). The junior name is not to be rejected, as the relevant taxa are no longer considered congeneric (ICZN 1999: Art. 59.2).

1.2 *Achillides krishna orientis* Schäffler, 2004: 3, pl. 4, figs. 1–4.

This name is normally regarded as belonging to *Papilio krishna* Moore, [1858]. Racheli & Bozano (2024) treated this taxon as a synonym of subspecies *charlesi* Fruhstorfer, 1902 without explanation.

A junior secondary homonym of *Papilio machaon orientis* Verity, 1911, currently regarded as a valid subspecies of *Papilio machaon* Linnaeus, 1758 (Takahashi & Kaymuk 1997: 153). Pending further investigation on its status, the taxon requires a replacement name. Proposed *nomen novum*: *Papilio krishna schaeffleri*.

1.3 *Achillides polycctor simoni* Sturm, 2006: 3, 12.

This name is normally regarded as belonging to *Papilio bianor* Cramer, 1777, probably only a junior synonym of nominate subspecies *bianor*, as stated by Hu *et al.* (2023).

A junior secondary homonym of *Papilio ucalegon* var. *simoni* Aurivillius, 1899, currently regarded as a valid species of *Graphium* Scopoli, 1777 (Smith & Vane-Wright, 2001: 663). The junior name is not to be rejected, as the relevant taxa are no longer considered congeneric (ICZN 1999: Art. 59.2).

1.4 *Achillides ulysses penelope* Dufek, Schäffler & Schmidbauer, 2005: 1, fig.

This name is normally regarded as a subspecies of *Papilio ulysses* Linnaeus, 1758.

A junior secondary homonym of *Papilio penelope* Fabricius, 1775, currently regarded as a valid species of *Cissia* Doubleday, 1848 – Nymphalidae: Satyrinae (Lamas 2004: 218), and of *Papilio penelope* Wallace, 1865, currently regarded as a junior subjective synonym of *Papilio ulysses autolytus* C. Felder & R. Felder, [1865] (Parsons, [1998]: 267). Requires replacement name. Proposed *nomen novum*: *Papilio ulysses zizi*. The proposed

name is an arbitrary combination of letters.

2. Junior Primary Homonyms covered by Article 23.9.5

The names in this section are all junior primary homonyms of taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. ICZN Code (1999) Article 23.9.5 clearly states that such junior homonyms must not automatically be replaced, cases should be referred to the ICZN for a ruling under the plenary power and meanwhile prevailing usage of names is to be maintained. Here six taxon names are recognised as junior primary homonyms to which Article 23.9.5 applies.

2.1 *Papilio arcturus arius* Rothschild, 1908: 174

Currently regarded as a valid subspecies of *Papilio arcturus* Westwood, 1842 (D’Abrera 1982: 55).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio arius* Cramer, 1775, a *nomen dubium* in *Calydna* Doubleday, 1847 – Riodinidae (Hall 2002: 229; Callaghan & Lamas 2004: 161). The homonymous names apply to taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. Case needs to be referred to the ICZN.

2.2 *Papilio ulysses dirce* Jordan, 1909: 84

Currently regarded as a valid subspecies of *Papilio ulysses* Linnaeus, 1758 (Shimogori 1997: 100).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio dirce* Linnaeus, 1758 (currently *Colobura dirce* [Linnaeus, 1758] – Nymphalidae: Nymphalinae) (Lamas 2004: 249). The homonymous names apply to taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. Case needs to be referred to the ICZN.

2.3 *Papilio telegonus* C. Felder & R. Felder, 1860: 226

Currently regarded as a valid subspecies of *Papilio ulysses* Linnaeus, 1758 (Shimogori 1997: 100).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio telegonvs* [sic] Bergsträsser, 1779 (currently regarded as a subjective synonym of *Phengaris teleius* (Bergsträsser, 1779) – Lycaenidae: Polyommatainae) (Tuzov *et al.* 2000: 156, as *Maculinea teleius*). The homonymous names apply to taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. Case needs to be referred to the ICZN. See also # 3.1 below.

2.4 *Papilio telemachus* Montrouzier, 1856: 401

Currently regarded as a valid subspecies of *Papilio ulysses* Linnaeus, 1758 (Shimogori 1997: 100).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio telemachus* Linnaeus, 1758 (currently *Morpho telemachus* [Linnaeus, 1758] – Nymphalidae: Morphinae) (Lamas 2004: 200). The homonymous names apply to taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. Case needs to be referred to the ICZN.

2.5 *Papilio ulysses gabrielis* Rothschild, 1898: 217

Currently regarded as a valid subspecies of *Papilio ulysses* Linnaeus, 1758 (Shimogori 1997: 100).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio gabrielis* Fabricius, 1781 (currently regarded as a junior objective synonym of *Evenus gabriela* [Cramer, 1775] – Lycaenidae: Theclinae) (Robbins 2004: 119). The homonymous names apply to taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. Case needs to be referred to the ICZN.

2.6 *Papilio bianor junia* Jordan, 1909: 78

Currently regarded as the valid name for the subspecies of *Papilio bianor* Cramer, 1777 from Ishigaki Island, southernmost Japan (Cotton 2025: 12).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio junia* Cramer, 1780 (currently regarded as a subspecies of *Cisandina lea* [Cramer, 1777] – Nymphalidae: Satyrinae) (Nakahara *et al.* 2022). The homonymous names apply to taxa not considered congeneric after 1899. Case needs to be referred to the ICZN.

3. Replacement Names proposed in contravention of Article 23.9.5

Although ICZN Code Article 23.9.5 does not specify the status of replacement names proposed after 1999 in contravention of the article, such names must be treated as junior objective synonyms of the junior homonyms to which Article 23.9.5 applies until such time as the ICZN Commission rules on the validity of the junior homonyms. One name recognised as having been proposed in contravention of this Article is discussed in this section.

3.1 *Papilio ulysses bepe* Koçak & Kemal, 2000: 4

Proposed as a new replacement name for *Papilio ulysses telegonus* Fruhstorfer [sic! = C. Felder & R. Felder, 1860].

Since the replacement name *bepe* Koçak & Kemal, 2000 was proposed in contravention of Article 23.9.5, which states that such names must not automatically be replaced, the name *Papilio ulysses bepe* Koçak & Kemal, 2000 must be considered as a junior objective synonym of *Papilio ulysses telegonus* C. Felder & R. Felder, 1860 (**new synonym**) until such time as the Commission rules on an application to consider the status of *Papilio ulysses telegonus* C. Felder & R. Felder, 1860. See # 2.3 above.

4. Junior Primary Homonyms still in use despite replacement before 2000

One name which was replaced before the year 2000 due to primary homonymy is recognised as still being treated as the valid name for a species-group taxon in subgenus *Achillides* despite being permanently invalid. Article 23.9.5 cannot apply to this name since it only applies to names identified as homonymous after 2000.

4.1 *Papilio daedalus* C. Felder & R. Felder, 1861: 298

Currently regarded as a species of *Papilio* Linnaeus, 1758 from the Philippines (Shimogori 1997: 98).

A junior primary homonym of *Papilio daedalus* Fabricius, 1775 (currently *Hamanumida daedalus* [Fabricius, 1775] – Nymphalidae: Limenitidinae) (Ackery *et al.* 1995: 424). Koçak (1996: 8) declared *Papilio daedalus* C. Felder & R. Felder, 1861 as a junior homonym and newly replaced it with *Papilio angustatus* [sic] *selma*.

The oldest available name for this taxon is *Papilio palinurus nymphodorus* Fruhstorfer, 1909 (type locality Bazilan). The senior name *Papilio angustatus Staudinger, 1888* becomes the valid name for the species which consists of two subspecies, *P. angustatus angustatus* Staudinger, 1888 and *P. angustatus nymphodorus* Fruhstorfer, 1909 (**new status**). The available names *Papilio daedalus terukoae* K. Okano, 1991 and *Papilio angustatus* [sic] *selma* Koçak, 1996 are junior subjective synonyms (**new synonyms**) of *Papilio palinurus nymphodorus* Fruhstorfer, 1909.

5. Seniority of Synonyms

In many situations prevailing usage clauses were introduced in the current Code (ICZN 1999) to ensure stability of nomenclature, but there are no such clauses covering the name in this section. Thus, despite the junior name being well known, the first published name becomes the valid taxon name.

5.1 *Papilio prillwitzi* Fruhstorfer, 1893a: 225

Described as a species but subsequently regarded as an aberration of *Papilio paris gedeensis* Fruhstorfer, 1893b (Jordan 1909: 80). *Papilio prillwitzi* was published in August 1893 whereas *Papilio arjuna* var. *gedeensis* Fruhstorfer, 1893b was published in a subsequent part of the same journal in September 1893.

Since the name *Papilio prillwitzi* was described as a species, subsequent determination that the holotype is an aberration does not affect the availability of the name. Thus, ***prillwitzi* Fruhstorfer, 1893** becomes the valid subspecies name for ***Papilio arjuna* Horsfield, [1828]** from West Java and the name *gedeensis* Fruhstorfer, 1893 is a junior subjective synonym (**new synonym**).

6. Names based on artefacts

6.1 *Papilio lorquini* Reakirt, [1865]: 462

This name was described based on a specimen provided by Ernest F. Lorquin; presumably obtained by his father, Pierre Joseph Michel Lorquin, on his visit to China and the Philippines between 1856 and 1860. Examination of the holotype housed in the Field Museum in Chicago, USA, clearly shows that it is an artefact composed of forewings of a male *Papilio paris paris* Linnaeus, 1758 attached by glue to the body and hindwings of *Papilio bianor bianor* Cramer, 1777 and thus must have originated in China. Images of the specimen, which are copyright of the Field Museum, are available from <https://collections-zoology.fieldmuseum.org/catalogue/807664>. Under ICZN Code Article 73.1.5, the forewings belonging to *Papilio paris* are hereby excluded from the holotype for the purposes of synonymy, and the name *Papilio lorquini* Reakirt, [1865] is considered a junior subjective synonym of *Papilio bianor* Cramer, 1777 (**new synonym**).

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● Additional information

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